

EFFICIENCY OF THE ACTIVITIES OF MANAGEMENT STAFF OF LOCAL EXECUTIVE AUTHORITIES ISSUE OF IMPROVING EVALUATION MECHANISMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16949598>

Abstract: issues of improving the mechanisms and criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of leading employees of local executive authorities were studied.

Keywords: local executive authorities, effectiveness, evaluation mechanism, KPIs, public administration.

Introduction:

In recent years, in order to introduce an effective system for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of managers of local executive authorities and the achievement of target indicators, a number of legislative acts have been adopted, and a new assessment system and unique experience have begun in our country.

The need to use specific criteria and indicators for accurate and objective assessment of the effectiveness of management activities in local executive authorities is growing.

Main part:

In accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 31, 2024, No. 463, the Regulation on Assessment of the Effectiveness of the Activities of Deputy Chairmen of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, khokims of regions, the city of Tashkent, and districts (cities) was approved, which defines the mechanisms and criteria for assessing the effectiveness [1].

In accordance with this Regulation, the development and approval of KPI indicators for managers will be carried out in a new order.

Under the new procedure, a systematic approach based on specific indicators and metrics in assessing the performance of managerial personnel in local executive authorities has not been sufficiently formed. The evaluation is based more on work experience, personal abilities, or the subjective opinion of higher-level managers. This limits the possibility of accurate in-depth analysis of effectiveness and rational management decision-making.

Therefore, the assessment of the activities of managers should be carried out in close connection with the goals and objectives of the organization, based on such key indicators as labor productivity, the effectiveness of decisions, the level of public satisfaction, and the introduction of innovations in management. The following categories of indicators are important in determining effectiveness:

- Performance KPIs: the level of fulfillment of established plans (for example: economic growth, new jobs, public satisfaction, etc.).
- Work process indicators: efficiency of time and resource use, practicality of management decisions.
- Indicators of social impact: attitude to public appeals, assessment of service quality, level of transparency and openness.

The introduction of such indicators serves to create a mechanism that allows for accurate, analytical, and predictive measurement of the manager's performance. In this case, it is advisable to use a digital platform and data analysis tools.

For assessing the effectiveness of public administration, the correct formation of KPI indicators and their development based on specific criteria is of great importance. Currently, legislative and organizational reforms are being carried out in Uzbekistan aimed at improving the mechanism for assessing the performance of civil servants. However, shortcomings in the existing system, in particular, the excessive number of indicators and their burden on the work process, negatively affect the effectiveness of civil servants. [2].

In his speech at the joint session of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the head of state emphasized that "practical effectiveness and the realization of the interests of the people must be the main criteria for evaluating the activities of each member of the government." [3].

Improvement of the mechanisms for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of leading employees of local executive authorities is of great importance in the modernization of the public administration system. An effective assessment system not only increases the responsibility and accountability of managers, but also stimulates their strategic thinking and the introduction of innovative approaches.

Also, the introduction of advanced mechanisms for assessing the activities of managers is an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of local

government bodies, strengthening citizens' trust in public administration, and ensuring socio-economic development.

Conclusion:

By assessing the effectiveness of the activities of managers of local executive authorities based on specific and systematic KPIs, it is possible to improve the quality of public administration in local executive authorities and strengthen the decision-making system in accordance with the interests of citizens.

In order to improve the mechanisms and criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of managerial personnel of local executive authorities, the following proposals have been developed:

KPI indicators should be formed taking into account industry specifics;

-when selecting KPIs, a correspondence between practical needs and expert assessments must be ensured;

-regular and frequent implementation of control and monitoring processes increases efficiency;

-the introduction of quality-oriented and result-oriented indicators will create an opportunity for objective assessment.

References:

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